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- Biomaterial Investigations in Dentistry
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- Frontiers in Nephrology
- Ukrains'kij Zurnal Vijskovoi Medicini
- Frontiers in Sleep
- Frontiers in Antibiotics
- Food Innovation and Advances
- Journal of Food Health and Bioenvironmental Science
- Electrical Measurement and Instrumentation
- IEEE Open Journal of Instrumentation and Measurement
- Journal of the International Clinical Dental Research Organization
- Journal of Diabetology
- Neurosurgery Practice
- Anuar de Lingvistica si Istorie Literara
- Studies in the Fantastic
- Frontiers in Photonics
- Journal of Electric Propulsion

- Mathematical Proceedings of the Royal Irish Academy
- Bulletin of the Polish Academy of Sciences. Mathematics
- International Journal of Ecosystems and Ecology Science
- International Journal of Noncommunicable Diseases
- Cambridge Prisms: Global Mental Health
- Tanta Dental Journal
- Radiation Environment and Medicine
- European Journal of Anaesthesiology and Intensive Care
- Interpreting and Society
- Mathematica Montisnigri
- Journal of the Canadian Association of Gastroenterology
- Publishing and Printing
- Journal of Zhengzhou University, Medical Sciences
- Modern Preventive Medicine
- Ibom Medical Journal
- Information studies: Theory and Application
- Journal of Stochastic Analysis
- Problems of Applied Mathematics and Mathematical Modeling
- Journal of Pediatric Critical Care
- Advanced Studies in Pure Mathematics
- SIAM Journal on Mathematics of Data Science
- 3D Printing in Medicine
- Cadernos de Fraseologia Galega
- Tsukuba Journal of Mathematics
- Chinese Journal of Underground Space and Engineering
- Jurnal Ilmiah Al-Syir'ah
- Journal of Liver Transplantation
- Natural Sciences (Weinheim, Germany)
- Vesnik of Yanka Kupala State University of Grodno. Series 2. Mathematics. Physics. Informatics, Computer Technology and its Control
- Journal of Highway and Transportation Research and Development
- Journal of Unmanned Undersea Systems
- Journal of Electronic Measurement and Instrumentation
- Acta Botanica Boreali-Occidentalia Sinica
- Studia Historica Brunensia
- Linguistische Treffen in Wroclaw
- Journal of Business Models
- Decisions Marketing
- Chinese Circulation Journal
- Clinical Immunology Communications
- Italian Journal of Computational Linguistics
- Cadernos do Arquivo Municipal

- Urbanform and Design
- Revue Internationale PME
- IdeAs
- Miscelanea de Estudios Arabes y Hebraicos Seccion Arabe-Islam
- Logopaedica Lodziensia
- Brill Research Perspectives in Popular Culture
- Journal of Machine Learning for Modeling and Computing
- Kronos: Southern African Histories
- Economic Geography
- Perm Journal of Petroleum and Mining Engineering
- Yingyong Qixiang Xuebao
- Online Journal of Public Health Informatics
- International Journal of Agricultural Science, Research and Technology in Extension and Education Systems
- Proceedings in Marine Technology and Ocean Engineering
- Revista de Investigaciones Universidad del Quindio
- Historia Economica e Historia de Empresas
- Journal of History of Science and Technology
- Petroleum Drilling Techniques
- Offshore Site Investigation and Geotechnics
- Studia Historiae Ecclesiasticae
- Studies in Science of Science
- Schutzian Research
- Lexis Supplementi
- American Economic Review - Insight
- Rivista di Diritto Internazionale Privato e Processuale
- Polski Proces Cywilny
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- Chinese Journal of General Practice
- Journal of African Development
- Collingwood and British Idealism Studies